

Exploração de Características Acústicas e Texturais em um Modelo de Stacking para a Anotação Automática de Tags Musicais

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		CAL3K															
		Etapla 1				Etapla 2				Etapla 2				Etapla 2			
		Precisao		Recall		Acuracia		F_Score		Precisao		Recall		Acuracia		F_Score	
		Media	Desvio Padrão	Media	Desvio Padrão	Media	Desvio Padrão	Media	Desvio Padrão	Media	Desvio Padrão	Media	Desvio Padrão	Media	Desvio Padrão	Media	Desvio Padrão
LBP	Media	0.46733	0.00624	0.46653	0.00519	0.83967	0.00249	0.46700	0.00535	0.47800	0.00356	0.47633	0.00287	0.84267	0.00170	0.47700	0.00294
	Desvio Padrão	0.44767	0.01050	0.45467	0.00732	0.83400	0.00356	0.46667	0.00899	0.47000	0.00572	0.46833	0.00287	0.84607	0.00189	0.46933	0.00368
	LBP	0.44133	0.00736	0.43967	0.00419	0.82333	0.00236	0.45033	0.00573	0.45933	0.00573	0.45733	0.00236	0.83733	0.00170	0.45867	0.00419
	GLCM	0.45233	0.00454	0.45233	0.00454	0.83500	0.00000	0.45233	0.00454	0.83500	0.00000	0.45233	0.00454	0.83500	0.00000	0.45233	0.00454
	MFC	0.45233	0.00454	0.45233	0.00454	0.83500	0.00000	0.45233	0.00454	0.83500	0.00000	0.45233	0.00454	0.83500	0.00000	0.45233	0.00454
	Zero Crossing Rate	0.35637	0.00651	0.35667	0.00450	0.80900	0.00082	0.35667	0.00450	0.80900	0.00082	0.35667	0.00450	0.80900	0.00082	0.35667	0.00450
	Spectral Rolloff	0.35367	0.00651	0.35367	0.00450	0.80533	0.00205	0.35367	0.00651	0.35367	0.00651	0.80533	0.00170	0.37200	0.00648	0.81067	0.00170
	Chroma	0.32333	0.00660	0.32333	0.00424	0.79633	0.00125	0.32400	0.00535	0.32333	0.00368	0.33333	0.00492	0.80500	0.00216	0.35267	0.00386
	Early Fusion	0.45933	0.00403	0.45733	0.00094	0.83733	0.00094	0.45833	0.00189	0.45733	0.00125	0.46933	0.00282	0.84000	0.00216	0.47000	0.00616
	Max	0.47000	0.00403	0.46800	0.00356	0.84033	0.00189	0.46900	0.00189	0.46167	0.00476	0.48000	0.00082	0.84800	0.00170	0.48100	0.00327
	Min	0.47000	0.00327	0.45367	0.00094	0.83167	0.00025	0.45667	0.00025	0.47033	0.00411	0.46667	0.00411	0.84667	0.00216	0.48000	0.00327
	Soma	0.48200	0.00565	0.48000	0.00214	0.84433	0.00170	0.48067	0.00340	0.48067	0.00340	0.48200	0.00082	0.84733	0.00170	0.49133	0.00205
	Prof	0.48300	0.00616	0.48033	0.00249	0.84467	0.00189	0.48200	0.00408	0.49333	0.00150	0.47667	0.00236	0.84733	0.00205	0.49200	0.00294
	Mediana	0.47067	0.01027	0.46000	0.00616	0.84100	0.00294	0.46967	0.00785	0.47900	0.00451	0.47667	0.00147	0.84267	0.00464	0.47767	0.01347
	Max	0.46300	0.00898	0.45700	0.00455	0.83767	0.00262	0.45833	0.00394	0.47767	0.00736	0.47433	0.00330	0.84267	0.00189	0.47633	0.00499
	Min	0.46300	0.00519	0.46033	0.00309	0.83867	0.00125	0.46200	0.00574	0.48533	0.00899	0.48167	0.00694	0.84500	0.00216	0.48333	0.00793
Soma	0.47133	0.01050	0.46800	0.00712	0.84100	0.00245	0.46967	0.00873	0.48867	0.00873	0.48567	0.00573	0.84633	0.00205	0.48700	0.01712	
Prof	0.47233	0.01100	0.46800	0.00726	0.84100	0.00245	0.47000	0.00849	0.48967	0.01084	0.48670	0.00779	0.84667	0.00249	0.48900	0.01942	
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